

A Study On Future Developments Of Artificial Intelligence And Quantum Computing

Krishna Prasad K

Associate Professor, Institute of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India

Orcid ID: 0000-0001-5282-9038;

E-mail: krishnaprasadkcci@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Anup Patnaik

Post Doctoral Research Fellow,
Institute of Engineering and Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India

Abstract: Artificial Intelligence and Quantum Computing are the latest Computing Technology of the 21st Century which has numerous applications in the field of Education, Entertainment, Healthcare, Security, and Commercial fields. Artificial Intelligence is more mature now compared to Quantum Computing and the latter one is still in its early stages and many top companies like Honeywell, Google, and IBM already invested a good amount of money in Research and development. Traditional Computing involves computation with a binary digit (bit) 1 and 0 whereas quantum computing involves Qubit and the information can have more than one or multiple states. Artificial Intelligence in simple words is making the computer system think, and respond to certain critical problems and provide the best solution like human beings. Quantum Computing is the traditional form of computing with new means or methods and which follows a similar rule of Atoms to manipulate or process Information. Artificial Intelligence system is strongly connected with the Internet of Things (IoT) for decision making and to provide the ideal solution when machines are connected with human beings. In this paper, we discuss on present and future developments of Artificial Intelligence and Quantum Computing and its contributions or relationship with other related fields of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). This paper also discusses future breakthroughs of these two technologies. This paper will make a real attempt to find the existing developments, future growth, and applications of Artificial Intelligence and Quantum Computing.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Quantum Computing, Qubit, Internet of Things, Information and Communication Technology, Healthcare Data Analytics.

1. Introduction

Quantum computing (QC) is setting up future trends of Artificial Intelligence (AI) development and is considered as a new weapon in the AI arsenal to solve many NP hard problems easily. The next generation of AI is termed as quantum Artificial Intelligence (QAI) which is having many trained machine learning models that establish an optimized

algorithm model. Both together can provide a computation boost and the speed of processing complex data and datasets will increase significantly. Quantum computing is the future of the computation world. It will not only increase the computation power but also help to answer the questions which remain unsolved because of the limitations of classical computers and algorithms.

The application of quantum computing can bring the innovative landscape in many sectors.

We also defined the terminologies of quantum mechanics which are used for information processing such as entanglement, superposition, interference, Coherence/decoherence, and speedup. Superposition states of a quantum system are similar to waves in classical physics which have the ability to hold multiple states so every quantum information can be represented as a sum of two or more other quantum states. The states are represented by qubits, so the group of qubits can define a multidimensional computation space where the complex problem can be represented in new means to resolve it.

Entanglement is a quantum property that correlates the behavior of two separate objects and connects qubits permanently entangling them together. When multiple qubits are entangled, changes to one qubit directly impact the other qubits. Quantum algorithms leverage those relationships to find solutions to complex problems. A quantum machine with 50 qubits capacity can examine two to the power of 50 i.e. (2^{50}) states simultaneously. The increase in power plus the entanglement of qubits allows quantum computers to solve problems efficiently, finding a solution faster, with fewer calculation efforts. The correlation between entangled qubits in quantum computing means measuring the state of one map to information about the state of the other. Interference is required to control the quantum states, possibly amplify the signals which are needed, and also reject the signals mapped to meaningless query

answers. Coherence/decoherence Quantum state information is very much prone to failure.

Classical computers have two states representation that can store the classical bits either 0 or 1 in the transistors, and these states can be measured with high certainty before timeout. Transistor-based classical computers are depending on these states to represent the data displayed as bits/bytes to the end users. Instead, quantum computers hold qubits, and their states are prepared by quantum superposition which embodies both 0 and 1 states.

So, a qubit data is the superposition of these two states written as:

$$\Psi = a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle \quad (1)$$

The coefficients a and b are called probability amplitudes. Both a and b can be complex numbers and must satisfy a condition:

$$|a|^2 + |b|^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

i.e. a normalization to unity. This is an analog of the convention that probabilities are set to sum to 1

In the Bloch sphere, Qubit state is represented by this symbol ($|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$) which allows us to consider multiple states at the same time.

Therefore, certainly it has the ability to handle some of the world's most difficult problems and calculations involved in healthcare, energy, environmental systems, and space exploration research areas. Because of its impressive potential, Shor's factorization quantum algorithm will provide an exponential speedup over classical computers, as it has simultaneous computation capability, in fields such as cryptography, chemistry, materials science, systems optimization, and machine learning/AI. Currently, IBM's 127-Qubit Eagle system, and Google TensorFlow Quantum software frameworks display improving the performance of our artificial neural networks through hybrid machine learning models. It handles large amounts of data, which is essential for training machine learning/artificial intelligence models. As quantum computing gains more traction, it will play a vital role in developing artificial intelligence and future applications. Since, AI models are growing in size to train their own models then the situation will get worse over time from a computation standpoint as it will take months to complete the flow.

QC has to deal with efficient quantum registers, quantum gates, and quantum algorithms to make quantum computers widely acceptable to all users to solve today's generation complex problems. Quantum supremacy primarily draws the difference between quantum computing and classical

computing. The Quantum supremacy concept highlights that quantum computing-based devices can provide a better solution than the classical computer (even supercomputers) with respect to computational speed, image processing, simulation and modeling, telecommunications, and different technological domains, thus affecting every application domain. Though the initial application of quantum technology has already been phased out, it is still far from being commercialized.

Existing research focuses on quantum computing and its technological background, whereas our study makes an effort to mark the beginning of quantum computing research with the below outlined points. So, the following are the main contributions of this paper:

1. This paper provides core fundamental concepts about QC and the comprehensive analysis of recent works done so far, and the road to exploring and assessing this area's growth.
2. Quantum computing is a blend of physics, Quantum mechanics, and information sciences, we established the relation between these two and source development frameworks/ programs to support.
3. It also provides a summary of past developments and also on the progress going on quantum information science.
4. We will provide a list of research developments on the quantum side of interest along with a high-quality list of reference resources for a more in-depth study of these domains.

2. Literature Review

In the contemporary corporate environment, fierce rivalry and technology upheavals have altered the way in which the firms function. A globally customer-centric methodology that prioritises customer requirements is crucial for organisational growth. The world's technological and industrial uprising has led to the widespread use of new generation information and communication technologies, in particular artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and blockchain technology. The government, manufacturing/production industry, and academic institutions are all paying considerable attention to artificial intelligence. The science of artificial intelligence is termed as AI. AI employs computers to replicate human intelligence and trains computers to adapt and learn human behaviour like learning, reasoning, and decision-making [1]. AI mimics human intellectual activity by acquiring knowledge, analysing, and studying the expressions and applies these approaches to produce results that are very

similar to those produced by human brains [2]. The key technologies that are covered under AI are machine learning, computer vision, data mining, pattern recognition, language processing, etc. The artificial intelligence has emerged in the stage of development recently owing to the evolution of big data, the introduction of deep learning, and the major encouragement of computer power. AI finds its implementation in a variety of end applications like health sector, e-commerce business, law, internet, transportation, internet, telecommunication, education, sustainable energy applications, agriculture, and other sectors, making it the primary driving force for the industry 4.0 revolution and the determining factor in escorting human society into the era of intelligence. The global advancement of science and technology is expanding rapidly towards digitalization, information, and intelligence [3]. Therefore, AI enables businesses to track real-time data for analysis and accomplish customer requirements quickly. Artificial intelligence (AI) provides useful information about client behaviour, which is crucial for attracting and customer retention. The use of AI prompts the consumer's next move and reformulate the entire interaction [4]. AI tools are valuable for determining client expectations and navigating the future. In today's corporate environment, Artificial Intelligence is applicable in a variety of contexts. Both professionals in the field and academicians feel that AI will play a vital role in the development of our society. As a result of the progression of technology, the globe has transformed into a complex web of interconnected networks. AI is implemented for big data analysis to learn about the market. These days, people engage with many forms of AI in the course of their regular tasks. For instance, the automatic e-mail filtering function, smartphones use Siri, Cortana, or Bixby, assistance during driving new vehicle. Artificial intelligence has come a long way in the last few decades, and experts have worked hard to make it better. The effort resulted in significant advancements such as big data analytics and machine learning applications in a variety of contexts and industries [5]. The upcoming AI breakthrough will not only provide computers more logical reasoning powers, but will also give them emotional capacities. Perception and behaviour are the foundations of intelligence. It doesn't necessitate any sort of understanding, modelling, or logic. To achieve AI's potential, it must gradually evolve, just like human intellect. It is also believed that artificial intelligence will soon overtake human intelligence [7].

On the other hand, quantum computing (QC) has lately shown amazing advancement by reaching unusually high computational performance benefits for specific jobs conducted on quantum computers that are ordinarily unsolvable by the most advanced supercomputers [6]. Due to its ability to leverage

quantum mechanical processes to execute calculations that are fundamentally distinct from those of conventional computers, quantum computers are capable of achieving such scientific achievements [8]. Quantum computing has gained substantial interest from the scientific community for the advancement of quantum approaches due to its vast applicability in numerous disciplines. The evolution of more complex quantum devices has increased its broad applicability usage, resulting in a surge in academic and industrial interest. Computational methods play significant roles in sustainable engineering and offers a cost-effective substitute to mathematical modelling and simulation for comprehending the behaviour of operating systems [9]. Although quantum computing is in its development phase, the advancement of the technology to make its commercial use is fairly new, and the scope of such usage is still rather minimal. It is envisaged that QC's computing will assist in tackling complicated and computationally difficult problems in medication design, data science, finance, etc. Quantum decoherence and qubit interconnection are two of the greatest obstacles to achieving quantum advantage in the coming years. QC is an extremely relevant and rapidly-evolving scientific field with considerable continuous advancements in all aspects. Introduction of hybrid algorithms takes benefits of both classical computing and quantum computing which enables creation of designs and provide varied solutions. The significant progress of quantum computing raises the question: how might this new computing approach help us accomplish the aims of AI.

3. Research Gaps

1. No specific algorithms to address the full control of decoherence to prevent loss of data.
2. Lack of designing optimized quantum circuits due to the high cost of building the system
3. Need generic liner algebra defining different quantum system
4. Need to find new design techniques for quantum computing
5. Exposure of machine learning to quantum computing paradigm for differential programming
6. Limited open source programming languages to fit the quantum requirement.
7. Recent break troughs in this paradigm are unable to provide higher qubit quantum computers from an operational perspective.
8. Fine integration of quantum data with classical processing or classical data with quantum processing is very difficult to realize at present. A hybrid design model between quantum computing with classical

computing would resolve many real world problems.

4. Future Trends of Artificial Intelligence and Quantum Computing

Design of Quantum Computers & Quantum Algorithms

The main component of quantum computers is the quantum algorithm which makes a significant impact on the execution of tasks. There are problems unsolved in conventional or classical approaches showing the hope to be resolved through quantum approaches with a high probability to provide correct answers. Problems that are undecidable in earlier approaches might be able to resolve by exploiting quantum superposition and quantum entanglement. Currently, the best-known algorithms are Shor's algorithm for factoring and Grover's algorithm for searching an unstructured database or an unordered list. Shor's algorithms run much (almost exponentially) faster than the best-known classical algorithm for factoring, the general number field sieve.[5] Grover's algorithm runs quadratically faster than the best possible classical algorithm for the same task a linear search.

Fig. 1. Basic Prototype Quantum Circuits Design

Quantum computers with these circuits are trained to get the expected output as neural networks. A qubit takes 2bits of data holding the probability of both state values(0 and 1), so for n bits machine then, a qubit can contain 2^n different values of states of the object. Photon is used to represent a qubit, so the superposition of qubits can be represented, encrypted then transmitted, and detected for the quantum states using this photon, a unit of light.

In classical computers, probability theory is represented through entropy, geometry vector using stochastic transformation, thus transform of probability distribution as below

Apply stochastic matrix to the P vector and normalize the output P vector applying 1-norm, the normalization process is a completely different implementation for quantum computers.

QAOA (Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm)

For variational circuits, one of the prime algorithms inspired by quantum annealing is QAOA which solves the discrete combinatorial optimization problems having a set of instances and every instance with a finite set of solutions. It will solve combinatorial optimization problems by finding an optimal object out of a finite set of objects.

The basic variational circuit design shown below in Fig. 2 has multiple components such as environment, Quantum processing unit, and classical computer

Fig. 2. Basic Variational Circuits Design

In the super conducting architecture, the quantum processing unit is embedded with a quantum environment and initiated different sorts of interactions but it has limited ability to control the system and also has minimum circuit depths, so to avoid the situation, we feed the output of the initial system to classical computers that provide required parameters to the quantum system to restart next set of operations.

QAOA, the variational algorithm is proposed by Farhi et al.[1] for combinatorial problems relies on unitary operators $U(\beta,\gamma)U(\beta,\gamma)$ characterized by the parameters (β,γ) on quantum state $|\psi(\beta,\gamma)\rangle$. These unitary operators are working on the state, that is the quantum superposition of all possible states in every iteration and after n^{th} number of iterations the cost function $C(z)$ is almost near to optimal, and the state being measured is close to being optimal state also.

Our aim here is to find the optimal object from the finite set of objects and the below equation gets the objective function to maximize value by summing up the boolean value of functions.

So, the combinatorial optimization problem for n-bit binary strings $(z) = Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_n$ and giving the output as 0 or 1

$$C_\alpha: \{0, 1\}^n \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$$

Cost function defined as below for n bits and m clauses

$$C(z) = \sum_{\alpha=1}^m C_{\alpha}(z)$$

The maximum or minimum value of $\langle H_P \rangle$ can be achieved by repeating the process to states of finding the optimal values for the parameters γ and β . The iterative process for finding optimal parameters uses classical optimization methods to do the required interactions with the quantum process, so QAOA is the best example of hybrid quantum-classical algorithms.

Problem Hamiltonian (H_P)

Finding the optimal value of the above objective function is also finding the extremal eigenvalues for the phase Hamiltonian. The phase Hamiltonian (H_P) maps the objective function $C(z)$ and acts diagonally on the computational basis states of 2^n dimensional Hilbert space or n-qubit space.

$$H_P |z\rangle = C(z)|z\rangle \tag{5}$$

Further, the phase operator is defined below $U_P(\gamma) = e^{-i\gamma H_P}$ and γ is a parameter.

Mixing Hamiltonian (H_B)

The mixing Hamiltonian H_M is defined as follows: $H_M = \sum_{j=1}^n \sigma_x^j$, (6)

where σ_x^j is the Pauli-X operator and n is identical to the n in (2). In quantum mechanical systems, Here Pauli-X operator acts as “NOT operator”, $\sigma_x^j |1\rangle = |0\rangle$ and $\sigma_x^j |0\rangle = |1\rangle$ (7)

the mixing operator is defined as follows, $U(\beta) = e^{-i\beta H_B}$ and β is a parameter (8)

The final state is prepared by applying these two unitaries as alternating blocks for P times

$$|\psi(\beta, \gamma)\rangle = U(\beta)U(\gamma) \cdots U(\beta)U(\gamma)|\psi_0\rangle \tag{9}$$

Where $|\psi_0\rangle$ - initial state and $|\psi(\beta, \gamma)\rangle$ - Final state

It will be more suitable for imperfect quantum computers.

Shor’s Algorithm

Its algorithm for finding the prime factors of an integer solves this problem in polynomial time $\log N$ for given integer N, rather than exponential time

achieved using classical algorithms. it consists of two phases

1. Turning the factoring problem into the problem of finding the period of a function (4)
2. Quantum Fourier Transform: finding quantum period finding through quantum parallelism

So, this factorization problem is translated into an order-finding problem which is resolved by using Quantum Phase Estimation (QPE) to the unitary operator, so an efficient period-finding algorithm can be applied to receive the integer factors efficiently. Therefore, compute the period of $(a^x \text{ mod } N)$ efficiently, then we can also find the factor efficiently in polynomial runtime. Run time on the classical computer is $O[\exp(L/3(\log L)^{2/3})]$ but that on the quantum computer is $O(L^3)$.

Given N & a are positive integers, don’t have any common factors, and $a < N$. The order or period defined as (r) is the smallest non-zero integer such that:

$$\text{Order function, } f(x) = a^x \text{ mod } N, \text{ where } \{ a^r \text{ mod } N = 1, a \in \mathbb{R} | 1 < a < N \} \tag{10}$$

Quantum phase estimation (QPE) applies to the unitary operator $U|y\rangle \equiv |ay \text{ mod } N\rangle$ (11)

It started with an initial state $|1\rangle$, after each successive application of the unitary operator (U), that will multiply the state of our circuit by $a \text{ (mod } N)$ and after r iterations, it will arrive at the state $|1\rangle$ again.

The superposition of the states in this second phase algorithm would be an eigenstate of U:

$$|u_0\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{r}} \sum_{k=0}^{r-1} |a^k \text{ mod } N\rangle \tag{12}$$

To get a unique eigenstate of computational basis states, the above equation is multiplied with an integer value of s where $0 \leq s \leq r-1$.

$$|u_s\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{r}} \sum_{k=0}^{r-1} e^{-\frac{2\pi i s k}{r}} |a^k \text{ mod } N\rangle$$

$$U|u_s\rangle = e^{\frac{2\pi i s}{r}} |u_s\rangle$$

Its first algorithm made researchers to realize the advantages of the quantum paradigm. This factoring algorithm has the execution in runtime polynomial, then runtime exponential of classical computers.

Grover's algorithm

Assume we are given a function $f: 0, 1^n \rightarrow 0, 1$

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x=x_0, \\ 0, & \text{if } x \neq x_0. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

I.e., we are looking for the binary number x_0 among all different 2^n possible numbers. The naive approach would be to check all 2^n instances of x and find when $f(x)=1$.

This algorithm searches an unordered database list for N entries with time complexity only $O(\sqrt{N})$ queries instead of the $O(N)$ queries required classical system. On a quantum computer with help of Grover's amplitude amplification trick, we can find the actual item in \sqrt{N} steps. The quadratic speedup is a significant time saving for finding items on a long list. Additionally, the algorithm does not use the list's internal data structure and creates its generic structure that's why it controls its quantum-defined processes to get the output. In this algorithm, multiple oracle black boxes are used (U_f, U_{F_0}), where queries are passed to get the answers, also known as diffusion operator. The oracle black boxes are repeated \sqrt{N} times. If the matches are multiple w , then the oracles are repeated $\sqrt{(N/t)}$ times. Grover search can also be used to search multiple matching elements.

Fig. 3. The basic circuit of Grover's algorithm,

So this circuit consists of a phase inversion oracle and also, a diffuser oracle which is iterated r times to get the w from the unsorted list.

Steps of this algorithm

1. Select a random value (w) from the unsorted list to search
2. Superposition of states after passing through Hadamard gate H .

$$|s\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} |x\rangle.$$

3. The phase inversion oracle U_f applies a conditional phase shift of -1 for the solution states
4. Apply H to each qubit of the state
5. Phase shift is applied to all states except the first one
6. Apply H to each qubit in the register
7. Iterate the process r times to find w item with a high probability
8. Check for a valid solution, if not then repeat the process again.

Deutsch-Jozsa Algorithm

Let's assume we have access to an oracle, a physical device that we cannot look inside, to which queries can be passed and returns answers as constant or balanced, then determine some property of the oracle using the minimal number of queries on a classical computer, such an Oracle is give by a function $f: \{0,1\}^n \rightarrow \{0,1\}^m$ and on a quantum computer, the oracle must be reversible.

Fig. 4. Circuit for DJ Problem with n qubits

To discuss Deutsch-Jozsa algorithm, it is better to start from the Deutsch algorithm where instead of n qubits, we just consider a single qubit. This will help us to ease our way towards understanding the usage of this algorithm. Classically, it requires $2^{n-1} + 1$ function evaluation in the worst case. Using the Deutsch-Jozsa algorithm, the question can be answered with just one function evaluation to decide whether constant or balanced function.

There are four steps in this algorithm described in below circuit diagram

Fig. 5. Circuit diagram

Step 1: Input having n qubits with all zeroes $|0^{\otimes n}\rangle$ and other qubit with $|1\rangle$

Step 2: Hadamard transformation on n qubits

$$|H^{\otimes n}\rangle |a\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^n}} \sum_{X \in \{0,1\}^n} (-1)^{a \cdot X} |X\rangle$$

Applying hadamard equation to the inputs, transformed to below expression 2^{n-1}

$$|\psi_1\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^{n+1}}} \sum_{x=0}^{2^n-1} |x\rangle(|0\rangle - |1\rangle)$$

Step 3: Now quantum oracle applied to the haramard expression to get more generic global expression i.e. $|x\rangle|y\rangle$ to $|x\rangle|y \oplus f(x)\rangle$

$$|\psi_2\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^{n+1}}} \sum_{x=0}^{2^n-1} |x\rangle(|f(x)\rangle - |1 \oplus f(x)\rangle)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^{n+1}}} \sum_{x=0}^{2^n-1} (-1)^{f(x)} |x\rangle(|0\rangle - |1\rangle)$$

Step 4: Back to apply the Hadamard transformation after quantum oracle transformation

$$|\psi_3\rangle = \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{x=0}^{2^n-1} (-1)^{f(x)} \left[\sum_{y=0}^{2^n-1} (-1)^{x \cdot y} |y\rangle \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{y=0}^{2^n-1} \left[\sum_{x=0}^{2^n-1} (-1)^{f(x)} (-1)^{x \cdot y} \right] |y\rangle$$

After measuring the first register using below equation that evaluates to 1 if $f(x)f(x)$ is constant and 0 if $f(x)f(x)$ is balanced

$$|0\rangle^{\otimes n} = \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{x=0}^{2^n-1} (-1)^{f(x)}$$

5. Conclusions

In this paper, basic understanding, and future scope of development for quantum computing are discussed, also how premium companies have invested a lot to analyze different aspects to reach reality. Further, Quantum supremacy will be a revolutionary moment in the computation world, if researchers can solve unknown issues that increase the decoherence for qubits. Because of its impressive potential, Shor’s factorization quantum algorithm will provide an exponential speedup over classical computers, as it has simultaneous computation capability, in fields such as cryptography, chemistry, materials science, systems optimization, and machine learning/AI. Currently, IBM’s 127-Qubit Eagle system and Google TensorFlow Quantum software frameworks display

improving the performance of our artificial neural networks through hybrid machine learning models. In the Bioch sphere, the Qubit state keeps multiple states at the same time taking advantage of the superposition and entanglement of quantum mechanics. The rationale for the convergence between artificial intelligence and quantum computing is discussed above and realized the technological importance.

References

- [1] Da Xu, Li, Yang Lu, and Ling Li. "Embedding blockchain technology into IoT for security: A survey." *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 8, no. 13 (2021): 10452-10473.
- [2] Duan, Lian, and Li Da Xu. "Business intelligence for enterprise systems: A survey." *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* 8, no. 3 (2012): 679-687.
- [3] Kuang, Lichun, L. I. U. He, R. E. N. Yili, L. U. O. Kai, S. H. I. Mingyu, S. U. Jian, and L. I. Xin. "Application and development trend of artificial intelligence in petroleum exploration and development." *Petroleum Exploration and Development* 48, no. 1 (2021): 1-14.
- [4] Tjepkema, L. "What Is Artificial Intelligence Marketing & Why Is It So Powerful." *Emarsys*: <https://www.emarsys.com/resources/blog/artificial-intelligence-marketing-solutions/03.05> (2019): 53-55.
- [5] Russell, Stuart J. *Artificial intelligence a modern approach*. Pearson Education, Inc., 2010.
- [6] Arute, Frank, Kunal Arya, Ryan Babbush, Dave Bacon, Joseph C. Bardin, Rami Barends, Rupak Biswas et al. "Quantum supremacy using a programmable superconducting processor." *Nature* 574, no. 7779 (2019): 505-510.
- [7] Haydari, Ammar, and Yasin Yilmaz. "Deep reinforcement learning for intelligent transportation systems: A survey." *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* (2020).
- [8] Nielsen, Michael A., and Isaac Chuang. "Quantum computation and quantum information." (2002): 558-559.
- [9] Gong, Jian, and Fengqi You. "Sustainable design and synthesis of energy systems." *Current Opinion in Chemical Engineering* 10 (2015): 77-86.